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UDC 539.175.1**HOUSE AND MEMORIAL MUSEUMS OF OUTSTANDING REPRESENTATIVES OF MUSICAL ART**

Mammadzade Vusala Vali – доктор філософії, доц.,
Азербайджанський університет туризму та менеджменту, Баку

Taking into account the trend of recent decades, we can note that museums can be called places of storage of not only tangible, but also intangible cultural heritage. In particular, we can attribute this to museums of literature, theater and music profile, because along with the material witnesses of the listed museums, their role in the development of society is investigated, promoted and demonstrated. We find it appropriate to introduce some of the music museums dedicated to the lives and works of numerous prominent figures in the field of music. Of course, it is not possible to discuss thousands of such museums, but it is necessary to provide information about a few interesting museums related to each group. The museums under study are institutions that carry out the collection, preservation, study and display of materials on the development of musical culture. The first proto-museums with a music focus began to emerge in Europe in the late 16th century, based on collections from musicians and theaters, as well as musical monuments preserved in churches and monasteries. These collections included manuscript scores of musical works, opera parts and play texts, and rare musical instruments (such as violin, viola, viol, cello, double bass, etc.) created by prominent artisans. Collections of musical instruments created by Italian artisans from the 16th to 18th centuries, such as Gasparo da Salò, Amati, Guarneri, Antonio Stradivari, Montagnana, Bergonzi, and Ruggieri, held the greatest material and artistic value. Historically, two major groups of music museums have formed worldwide. The first group includes museums focused on displaying items from various eras, cultures, and artistic schools. For example, the Museum of the History of European Instruments in Trondheim, the A. Stradivari Museum in Cremona, and others. The second group comprises the heritage of the world's prominent musical figures. Museums dedicated to V.A. Mozart in Salzburg, J.S. Bach in Eisenach, L. Beethoven in Bonn, N.A. Rimsky-Korsakov in Saint Petersburg, F.I. Chaliapin in Kislovodsk, Solomiya Krushelnyska in Lviv, and others. Museums worldwide and in Azerbaijan, including music museums, stand out for their unique collections and archives. It is our duty to preserve these values and pass them on to future generations.

Key words: Music, museum, memorial, opera, conductor, exposition, fund, collection.

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UDC 962.48**ЗАСОБИ ВИКОРИСТАННЯ ЗРАЗКІВ ВІТЧИЗНЯНОГО ТА СВІТОВОГО МИСТЕЦТВА
У НАВЧАЛЬНОМУ ПРОЦЕСІ ПОЧАТКОВИХ КЛАСІВ**

Sariyya Huseynli Safar – PhD student, Azerbaijan University of Languages
<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-7199-3096>

Показані способи використання зразків національного і світового мистецтва в навчальному процесі молодших класів і розповідається про важливість цього у формуванні світогляду учнів, розвитку естетичних почуттів і прищеплення моральних якостей. Автор спеціально представила результати своєї дослідницької роботи.

Таким чином, етичні та естетичні норми, сформовані в азербайджанському суспільстві і володіють високими моральними цінностями, можуть бути інтегровані в загальнолюдські ідеї завдяки своєму гуманістичному характеру. Як показує практика, національно-духовні цінності, культурна спадщина та історичні реалії, що передаються азербайджанським народом із покоління в покоління, з цікавістю сприймаються народами світу. У той же час світова культура і загальнолюдські цінності також стають чинником розвитку духовного життя нашого народу.

Ключові слова: навчання, навчальний процес, початкові класи, мистецтво, загальнолюдська та національна культура.

Examples of art, works of art, oral folk literature, fairy tales, riddles, Bayati, folk songs, seasonal and ceremonial songs and folklore examples of our people from time to time have been one of the important means of spiritual enrichment and formation of people as a nation. At the same time, the study of universal culture, values and examples of art has allowed people to trace and evaluate the events taking place in the world.

One of the main tasks of the education system in the «state strategy for the development of education in the Republic of Azerbaijan» is defined as follows:

- to prepare modern-minded and competitive personnel who protect and develop national moral and universal values, have a wide world view, are able to evaluate initiatives and innovations, have theoretical and practical knowledge [1].

«Understanding of universal human values, mastering it reflects the content of upbringing. These are morality, spirituality, ethics, labor, aesthetics, physical culture, nature protection, etc. it consists of the basis of the basic, basic culture of the personality» [2; 13]. In this regard, the study and promotion of national and Universal samples of culture and art plays an important role in the comprehensive development of modern students.

Art has always been a powerful means of expression, incorporating various cultures that exist in the world. Through art, we can learn the customs, traditions, history and lifestyle of different peoples.

The purpose of the research work conducted can be formulated as follows:

- to draw students' attention to the world of beauty by using examples of art in teaching various subjects. In this area, to introduce folk art, the works of artists and sculptors of national and other peoples. To listen to folk music and world music, show feature and documentary films, present the culture, folklore of different peoples and develop aesthetic feelings in students;

- to form a number of skills, habits and abilities in creative activity in students by using art forms in the process of teaching various subjects: to compare their own ideas with what they see and read in the surrounding world; to expand knowledge about each example of art and apply it to the topics given in the subjects; to embody the impressions received in their own creativity [4].

Art plays a special role in the formation and expression of the cultural identity of each person. It reflects the essence of a nation's beliefs, traditions, and life experiences, preserving them for future generations.

Azerbaijan is a rich country containing cultures of different nations. It is no coincidence that the statues, memorial plaques of prominent figures, writers, composers, heroes of other nations have been immortalized in Baku and other cities. And the information obtained about them is communicated to students in the learning process. In addition, statues and memorial plaques of prominent figures of Azerbaijan have been erected in various countries and the local population has been informed about them.

Azerbaijan is a rich country containing cultures of different nations. It is no coincidence that the statues, memorial plaques of prominent figures, writers, composers, heroes of other nations have been immortalized in Baku and other cities. And the information obtained about them is communicated to students in the learning process. In addition, statues and memorial plaques of prominent figures of Azerbaijan have been erected in various countries and the local population has been informed about them.

As an example of what we have said above, the monument of the prominent statesman of the Turkish state Mustafa Kemal Atatürk in front of the Turkish Embassy, the monument of the Ukrainian writer Taras Shevchenko on Azadlig Avenue, the monument of the Austrian composer Wolfgang Mozart in front of the Pedagogical College, and the monument of the Romanian composer George Enescu on Jafar Khandan Street are clear examples of this.

As we have noted, the memory of prominent figures of Azerbaijan has also been immortalized in a number of foreign countries. The erection of a statue of Heydar Aliyev in the Turkish cities of Kars, Istanbul, Izmir, Belgrade in Serbia, Ganatir in Egypt, Bucharest in Romania and Tbilisi in Georgia, and the bust of the Great Leader at the entrance to the Azerbaijani embassy in Kiev in Ukraine are proud facts. At the same time, a statue of the great Azerbaijani poet Nizami Ganjavi has been erected in the Italian capital of Rome, Acapulco in Mexico, Luxembourg, Tashkent, Ljubljana in Slovenia and other cities [3].

It is a proud event that a memorial monument to the brave and heroic oğlu of Azerbaijan, hero of the Soviet Union Mehdi Hanifa Oğlu Huseynzade (Mikhailo) was erected in Chepovani settlement of Slovenia. A Memorial Museum of Mehdi Huseynzade was opened in Shempas settlement of Nova Gorisa region.

Information about all this broadens the worldview of students, instills patriotic feelings in them, and they get acquainted with works of art related to sculpture.

Art in the learning process – can be considered as the inclusion of the study of art in the education system in general. Teachers collaborate with artists, cultural institutions and art institutions to integrate art into the curriculum.

«To instill a sense of beauty in young children, one of the main conditions is to carry out the following tasks:

a) to aesthetically educate children the ability to perceive and understand beauty in nature, human activity, art;

b) to develop in children the aesthetic artistic taste that arises in connection with the perception of these aesthetic beauties;

c) artistic creativity in children (singing, drawing, reciting poetry, storytelling, making, installation, applique etc.) to form and create a sense of sympathy for the beauties around him» [3; 365]. Referring to the author's ideas, it is appropriate to strive for the use of examples of art in teaching various subjects so that students not only acquire creative skills, but also form artistic taste in them, and understand them, not being indifferent to beauty.

Art helps students develop self-confidence, express their thoughts and feelings, and find their place in society. Students are able to talk about their work and explain their ideas, which helps them develop communication skills and confidence.

Art helps develop emotional intelligence, understand and interpret emotions. Painting, music and dance convey complex feelings and evoke emotional reactions. It teaches us to look at problems from different perspectives and find innovative solutions.

Undoubtedly, art plays an important role in shaping the worldview prevailing in a particular society. Its types are tools that reflect values and understand the key moments of life closer to people.

Art is able to help us understand our history, culture, life and the experiences of others in a way that can be achieved through various means. Art helps people to realize themselves, to express their inner world – their ideas and dreams. It also creates an incentive to realize their desires and desires in real life. Therefore, the role of the use of art in the learning process in the life of students is invaluable.

The importance of art in education is that studying music, fine arts, watching cinema and theater performances expands the imagination and helps develop creative abilities.

Through art samples, students express their thoughts, emotions and feelings and demonstrate this on paper, in music.

Observations show that the use of art samples in the learning process also has a positive effect on increasing the cultural level of students. In this regard, the teacher's presentation of national types of art and at the same time bringing music and art samples of different peoples into the learning process encourages students to comprehend beauty and the world. Art is a field that helps people come together and create unity. Creating and performing music together, working in collaboration with others allows students to have certain skills, appreciate art, be able to see and more deeply perceive aspects different from ourselves. In this regard, we bring to your attention a fragment of the lesson “Azerbaijani language” in the III grade.

Using examples of fine arts in the lesson of the «Azerbaijani language» in the 3rd grade.

Subject: Essay on pictures.

Purpose: uttering the content of the picture on the basis of creative imagination.

Tasks:

1. To develop creative imagination and figurativeness of ideas. Improving reading habits and communicative speech. To enrich the active vocabulary of students by various lexical means.

2. To be able to present and glorify his own country.

3. To develop aesthetic culture.

Supply: projector, interactive blackboard, paper.

1. Phonogram – Play the music «Dance of the Flowers» from the ballet «The Nutcracker».

2. T. Narimanbekov's «Rockets and Lilies», S. Bahlulzadeh's «Blooming Garden».

3. Poems of Azerbaijani poets about flowers.

I. Mirvarid Dilbazi «spring holiday».

The teacher reads M. Dilbazi's poem «Spring Festival», then addresses the children:

In what phrases does the poet glorify spring?

What flowers compare the patterns of the carpet?

Let us together describe the flowers in figurative expressions (beautiful fragrant jasmine, tulips that adorn the Meadows, Golden Rose that shares the joy of people, Iris that does not bend its shape, Rose of love zambag etc.).

II. Students also read the poem and make comparisons.

III. Creative work. «Guys, tell us about the flowers you like now. Come up with a little story and tell it. Name your story».

IV. During sports minutes, children describe butterflies flying over flowers to the sounds of Johann Strauss's «Viennese Waltz». Then the teacher shows the pictures of T. Narimanbeyov and S. Bahlulzadeh and asks:

- What mood is there in the pictures?

- What colors did the artist use?
- What season do these pictures remind you of? [5]

And now let's all take a picture of the grass together. This will be everyone's favorite rose on the lawn.

Children draw a picture of a meadow on large paper, and each of them recreates his favorite rose in the meadow. This work is carried out to the sound of the music «waltz of Roses». When the work is done, the children hang the painting from the blackboard and give it the name «Meadow fairy tale».

At the end, the teacher addresses the children: «Did you like the lesson? What did you learn in this lesson?»

While introducing the students to the beauties of nature, the waltz No. 7 by the Polish composer Frederic Chopin is played. The teacher's use of this music to create more beautiful feelings and make the attitude towards nature more memorable in students gives positive results.

Using examples of art in the learning process helps students develop language skills, social skills, decision-making, courage and creativity.

Every nation has its own ideas and customs that they value for their culture. Artists are the products of the society and culture in which they grow up. They are influenced by the customs and norms of their society. Often, their artwork reflects and supports the objects, ideas, and practices that society values.

Studying examples of art in the learning process means that students are active participants in their understanding and presentation. Through this art, students will learn more deeply about the author's concept. For example, if a few of the students can portray the hero of the work they read as it is in the picture, they can figuratively express the clothes, ideas, customs, culture of that time in general.

Summing up, it is possible to determine the following functions of examples of art:

- a) aesthetic function. Allows you to revive reality according to the laws of beauty; forms aesthetic taste;
- b) the social function is manifested in the ideological impact of art on society; thereby promoting social reality.

The teacher's professional enthusiasm, developed pedagogical thinking, creativity and the entire set of psychological and pedagogical knowledge, skills open up wide opportunities for students to perfectly master the examples of art.

The use of art samples in the learning process enriches the school experience and also prepares students for after-school life. These patterns encourage self-expression and creativity and are able to create a sense of self-confidence and individuality.

Thus, today the main goals of the use of art samples in the learning process can be formulated as below:

- a) aesthetic: to give pleasure and motivate;
- b) expressive: convey emotions and feelings at a deeper level;
- c) communicative: generalizing ideas and ideas, generating reactions, going beyond traditional communication, understanding universal values.

Examples of art can shape aesthetic taste, make our daily life more beautiful and interesting, but they can also create public opinion.

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WAYS TO USE SAMPLES OF NATIONAL AND WORLD ART IN THE LEARNING PROCESS OF ELEMENTARY GRADES

Sariyya Huseynli Safar – PhD student, Azerbaijan University of Languages

The article shows ways to use national and world art samples in the learning process of primary grades and talks about the importance of this in the formation of students' worldview, the development of aesthetic feelings and the instillation of moral qualities. The author specifically presented the results of her research work.

The following conclusions can be drawn from the research work conducted:

1. In order to effectively use examples of art in teaching various subjects in primary grades, four pedagogical conditions are important:

- training of teachers in this area;
- providing the learning process with appropriate equipment;

- stimulating primary school students to use art samples in an original and effective way, studying the inclinations and interests of each of them;

- including appropriate art samples in the learning process in the materials provided in textbooks.

2. The main principle determining the success of the pedagogical activity of a primary school teacher is a careful attitude to children's creativity, an understanding of which art sample each of them is more inclined to, their abilities (according to H. Gardner's theory), and at the same time careful management of this process.

3. It is necessary for a primary school teacher to know that constantly changing social values, an increasing flow of information are always reflected in art. Only truly spiritual works of art are immortal. Therefore, examples of classical painting, sculpture, crafts and folk art formed the basis of the content of the subject area.

4. In the process of research, the features of the formation of creative abilities of Primary School students were revealed. A differential approach was provided, taking into account the interest and individual-psychological characteristics of each of the students in a certain type of art. The introduction of the main directions of using the types of art samples gave positive results.

5. The use of computer technology when using art samples in teaching various subjects gave positive results:

- any topic accompanied by the demonstration of videos, photographs, reproductions of art samples of different peoples aroused great interest in students;

- the largest museums of the world were «visited»;

- students were «immersed» in space and time;

- students enthusiastically performed independent work;

- the learning process was activated.

6. The most successful activity for a teacher is to teach students with joy without any compulsion, develop their creative abilities and thereby improve the quality of the lesson.

Thus, ethical and aesthetic norms formed in Azerbaijani society and having high moral values can be integrated into universal ideas due to their humanistic character. As practice shows, national and spiritual values, cultural heritage and historical realities passed down by the Azerbaijani people from generation to generation are met with interest by the peoples of the world. At the same time, world culture and universal human values are also becoming a factor in developing the spiritual life of our people.

Key words: study, learning process, primary grades, art, universal and national culture.

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ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ ВПЛИВУ ФОРМУЮЧОГО ОЦІНЮВАННЯ НАВЧАННЯ ЗДОБУВАЧІВ ВИЩОЇ ОСВІТИ Gulnara Iskandarova – PhD student of Azerbaijan University of Languages

Формативне оцінювання – це потужний інструмент для покращення навчального процесу студентів у вищій освіті, що надає безперервний зворотний зв'язок під час навчання. На відміну від суммативних оцінок, які оцінюють студентів наприкінці курсу чи розділу, формативне оцінювання дає можливість отримувати оперативну інформацію, яка допомагає як викладачам, так і студентам виявляти галузі для покращення, уточнювати стратегії викладання та підвищувати результати навчання. Цей тип оцінювання сприяє активному залученню студентів, оскільки вони отримують своєчасний зворотний зв'язок, що дозволяє їм брати на себе відповідальність за своє навчання та вносити корективи на основі їхнього прогресу.

Різноманітні стратегії формативного оцінювання, включаючи взаємну оцінку, самооцінку та коригування викладача, є ключовими для його ефективності. Взаємний зворотний зв'язок сприяє співпраці та відповідальності серед студентів, а самооцінка розвиває метакогнітивні навички, допомагаючи студентам осмислювати їхнє навчання та ставити цілі для покращення. Ці стратегії не лише покращують академічну успішність, а й сприяють розвитку важливих навичок, таких як критичне мислення, саморегуляція та стійкість. Формативне оцінювання спонукає студентів сприймати помилки як можливості для зростання, а не як невдачі, підтримуючи ростове мислення та підвищуючи мотивацію.

Ключові слова: Формативне оцінювання, залучення, мотивація, зворотний зв'язок, педагогічна практика, досягнення, метакогнітивні навички

The use of assessment data to modify instruction to meet the requirements of students as determined by the evaluation forms the basis of this conceptualization. This concept allows for a variety of formative assessment strategies. Formative assessment is defined in one way as the process by which teachers evaluate students' learning in order to provide them feedback or alter lesson plans to better suit the requirements of the students [2; 45]. The significance of students actively participating in the formative assessment procedures is emphasized by two additional strategies [2; 50]. In one of these methods, students help each other learn by providing peer evaluation and feedback and by making suggestions to one another on how to accomplish their learning objectives [20; 116]. In the alternative method, the emphasis is on the students as autonomous learners